

Nitrogen Fixation in Slightly Alkaline Soil in Presence of Calcium Salts

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The effectiveness of eight calcium salts viz., calcium carbonate, di-calcium phosphate, calcium oxide, calcium sulphate, calcium sulphite, calcium sulphide, calcium acetate and calcium citrate on nitrogen fixation in a slightly alkaline soil was observed. It was found that the calcium salts, in general, enhance the nitrogen status of soil, the extent being dependent on the presence or absence of soil moisture, time and the nature of anionic parts of the calcium salts added.

THE study of nitrogen fixation by soil is quite old. The literature on the subject is voluminous for its obvious importance in the field of agriculture. However, it appears that the effect of calcium salts besides lime and liming materials on nitrogen fixation by soil is little studied.

In the following lines, results obtained on nitrogen fixation by the soils in presence of a few calcium salts have, therefore, been incorporated and discussed. Incidentally, it may be mentioned here that the results given in this paper are those obtained with the addition of 16 m.e. of calcium salts, which is found to be the optimum concentration of all the calcium salts observed to give maximum nitrogen fixation. The amount of nitrogen fixed was found to increase with the increase of calcium salt concentration from 1 m.e. to 16 m.e. per g. soil.

Experimental

The slightly alkaline soil sample was collected by the usual methods from district Jaunpur (U.P.) from a depth of 0-20 cm. The collected soil was then dried in the laboratory and after removing coarser particles, is passed through 100-mesh sieve (B.S.S.). It was then chemically analysed by the usual procedure¹.

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL COMPOSITION FOR JAUNPUR SOIL (0 to 20 cm depth)

Constituents	%
Loss on-ignition	7.95
HCl-insoluble	70.87
Fe ₂ O ₃	5.22
Sesquioxide	11.90
Total CaO	0.68
Total Na ₂ O	0.31
Total MgO	0.89
Total K ₂ O	0.65
Total P ₂ O ₅	0.48
Total Nitrogen	0.08
Total Organic Carbon	0.38
Total Organic Matter	0.65
Total Soluble Salts	0.25

C/N ratio	4.75
pH	8.50
Total B.E.C.	17.20 m.e. per 100 g.
Exchangeable Calcium	8.25 " " "
Exchangeable Potassium	3.46 " " "
Exchangeable Magnesium	2.20 " " "
Exchangeable Sodium	2.24 " " "

MECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF SOIL

Coarse sand	19.20
Fine sand	50.30
Silt	10.00
Clay	20.00

Texture : *Sandy Clay Loam*

For observing the effect of calcium salts on nitrogen fixation in this soil the following three treatments were given to the soil sample.

Treatment A :

The soil was saturated thrice with distilled water and before the second and third saturations, was dried in the air. After the third and last saturation, calcium salts equivalent to 1 m.e.; 2 m.e.; 4 m.e.; 8 m.e.; 16 m.e. and 20 m.e. were added per 100 g. of water-saturated soil and kept for one and two months.

Treatment B :

In this case, the soil was saturated thrice with distilled water and dried thrice after each saturation. After the third drying, the calcium salts were added in a similar fashion as in 'A' and kept for one and two months respectively.

Treatment C :

In this case, the soil was not treated with wetting and drying processes but in the same soil, calcium salts were added in a similar fashion as in 'A' and 'B' and kept for one and two months respectively.

For each saturation 55 ml. of distilled water were required for 100 g. of the experimental soils.

For each set, a control having all the treatments except calcium salts addition was also run side by side.

After one and two months, the experimental plates containing the soil were analysed for total nitrogen by salicylic acid method¹. The initial pH values of the treated soils after the addition of calcium salts were determined before these were kept for incubation whereas the final pH values were taken after the incubation of treated soils. pH measurements² were made electrometrically by Leeds-Northrup pH meter operated on 220V., 50 cycle a.c. mains. The ratio of soil and water was kept 1 : 2.5.

Results and Discussion

A perusal of tables 1 and 2 will clearly show that the addition of calcium salts in general, enhances the nitrogen status of the soil. The extent of enhancement is, however, observed to depend not only on the time of experimentation (one and two months) but also on the nature of soil treatments (Treatment A, B and C) and calcium salts. In general, it appears that nitrogen fixation in plates kept for one month is greater than those kept for two months. However, there are few exceptions to this general trend viz., calcium carbonate (A & C), calcium citrate (A, B & C), calcium sulphate and calcium sulphide (A). In case of one month experimental plates, addition of calcium salts increases nitrogen fixation more in soil given treatment B which is followed by treatment C and the last position being occupied by soils given treatment A. This order in case of soil kept for two months is as follows :

The efficiency order of calcium salts in relation to nitrogen fixation for each experimental period and treatment has been observed to lie in the following fashion :

One Month Experimental Period

Treatment A : $\text{CaHOP}_4 > \text{Ca}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 > \text{CaS} > \text{Ca-citrate} > \text{CaCO}_3 > \text{CaO}; \text{CaSO}_4 > \text{CaSO}_3 >$
 Treatment B : $\text{CaS} > \text{Ca-citrate} > \text{CaHPO}_4; \text{CaSO}_3 >$
 $\text{CaO} > \text{CaCO}_3 > \text{CaSO}_4 > \text{Ca}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 >$
 Treatment C : $\text{Ca}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 > \text{CaS} > \text{CaSO}_4 > \text{CaHOP}_4 > \text{CaCO}_3 > \text{CaO} > \text{CaSO}_3 >$
 Ca-citrate.

Two Months Experimental Period

Treatment A : $\text{Ca-citrate} > \text{CaS} > \text{Ca}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 >$
 $\text{CaCO}_3 > \text{CaSO}_4 > \text{CaO} > \text{CaHPO}_4 >$
 $\text{CaSO}_3 >$
 Treatment B : $\text{CaS} > \text{Ca-citrate} > \text{CaSO}_4 > \text{CaCO}_3 >$
 $\text{Ca}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 > \text{CaHPO}_4 > \text{CaO}; \text{CaSO}_3 >$
 Treatment C : $\text{Ca}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 > \text{CaSO}_4 > \text{CaS} > \text{Ca-citrate}; \text{CaCO}_3 > \text{CaHPO}_4 > \text{CaSO}_3 >$
 CaO.

From the above orders, it may be observed that for the one month period if the soil is under constant moisture supply (Treatment, A), di-calcium phosphate is most effective in increasing nitrogen fixation, where the moisture supply is minimum (Treatment,

C) and drying condition prevalent (Treatment, B), calcium acetate and calcium sulphide additions appear to be more fruitful. However, for the longer period of experimentation (two months), in case of treatment A, calcium citrate occupies the most effective position. In treatment—B and C this position is occupied by calcium sulphide and calcium acetate respectively. It is interesting to note further that, barring calcium carbonate and calcium oxide where nitrogen fixation increases with an increase in the resultant pH (vide tables 1 and 2), the fixation of nitrogen by this soil in presence of other calcium salts is generally accompanied by a decrease in the resultant (final) pH.

From the foregoing observations, it may be pointed out that the lesser nitrogen status in cases of the plates kept for two months than the one month plates may be due to greater nitrogen loss occurred in the former plates than the latter. However, as pointed out earlier, this loss is checked and in fact the total nitrogen fixed in case of two months' plates is actually increased in presence of calcium carbonate (A & C), calcium citrate (A, B, C), calcium sulphate and calcium sulphide (A). This is probably due to the fact that the optimum time of maximum nitrogen fixation in presence of the calcium salts has been passed. It is true that in case of treatment B, there is a greater nitrogen fixation than either treatment C or A in case of the one month experimental plates, yet a constant supply of moisture (treatment, A) appears to check the greater nitrogen loss in the longer run, as will be evident in Table 2 given for the two months experimental plates.

It is interesting to observe the Fischer's 't' values calculated from the observations in each table. The 't' values obtained for nitrogen fixed at 16 m.e. of calcium salts/100 g. soil are 5.0, 7.69 and 10.52 under treatment A, B and C respectively in one month's experimental time. These values under treatments A, B, C in two months' time of reaction are 6.25, 7.69 and 11.54 respectively. All these values are found to be greater than the calculated 't' value at 5% level of significance for 7 d.f. which is 2.365, clearly showing that the addition of calcium salts to slightly alkaline soil definitely increases nitrogen fixation.

While nitrogen fixation by photo-chemical means³ cannot be ignored yet it appears that greater fraction of fixation is as a result of the activities of the nitrogen fixing soil azotobacters which are very common in soils of tropical countries. Incidentally, it may be mentioned that soils of pH 7.2 are better for anchoring greater number of azotobacter cells for appreciable gain in fixed nitrogen on incubation⁴. It may be seen that the addition of calcium salts has kept the pH of the soil not below than 7.2 neither much higher as will affect the growth of nitrogen-fixing azotobacters. The difference in efficacy of the calcium salts appears to be due to the different anions they carry.

Since generally, the fixation is accompanied by the decrease in the resultant soil pH, the explanation given by Wilson and Burris⁵ for the nitrogen fixation

TABLE 1.—NITROGEN FIXATION IN SLIGHTLY ALKALINE SOIL IN PRESENCE OF CALCIUM SALTS (16 M.E. PER 100 G. SOIL) IN ONE MONTH DURATION.

Ca-salt	TREATMENT 'A'				TREATMENT 'B'				TREATMENT 'C'						
	N.fixed g-100g soil		pH		N.fixed g-100g soil		pH		N.fixed g-100g soil		pH				
	N.fixed at 16 m.e. of Ca-salts per 100g (X × 10 ²)	Increased than value in control lbs./acres (X × 10 ²)	Initial	Final	N.fixed at 16 m.e. of Ca-salts per 100g (X × 10 ²)	Increased than value in control lbs./acres (X × 10 ²)	Initial	Final	N.fixed at 16 m.e. of Ca-salts per 100g (X × 10 ²)	Increased than value in control lbs./acres (X × 10 ²)	Initial	Final			
Ca CO ₃	10.09	1.19	178.50	8.65	8.80	10.60	1.65	247.50	8.65	8.95	10.31	1.82	273.00	8.75	9.10
Ca HPO ₄	10.90	2.00	300.00	8.35	8.30	10.88	1.93	289.50	8.45	8.40	10.48	1.98	293.00	8.55	8.45
CaO	10.08	1.18	177.00	8.65	8.85	10.86	1.91	301.50	8.90	9.15	10.24	1.74	261.00	8.85	8.95
CaSO ₄	10.08	1.18	177.00	8.30	7.80	10.20	1.25	187.50	8.15	7.90	10.88	2.38	357.00	8.00	7.40
CaSO ₃	9.80	0.90	135.00	8.80	8.75	10.88	1.93	274.50	8.80	8.60	10.00	1.90	225.00	8.95	8.35
CaS	10.50	1.60	240.00	7.95	7.70	11.60	2.65	397.50	8.15	7.90	10.55	2.55	382.50	7.95	7.80
Ca(CH ₃ COO) ₂	10.80	1.90	285.00	8.15	7.05	10.08	1.13	169.50	8.40	8.35	10.80	2.30	345.00	8.15	7.50
Ca-citrate	10.29	1.39	208.50	8.40	8.35	10.92	1.97	195.00	8.60	8.45	10.08	1.88	237.00	8.40	8.45
Control	8.90	—	—	8.50	8.50	8.95	—	—	8.50	8.50	8.50	—	—	8.60	8.50

TABLE 2.—NITROGEN FIXATION IN SLIGHTLY ALKALINE SOIL IN PRESENCE OF CALCIUM SALTS (16 M.E. PER 100 G. SOIL) IN TWO MONTHS DURATION.

Ca-salt	TREATMENT 'A'				TREATMENT 'B'				TREATMENT 'C'						
	N.fixed g-100g soil		pH		N.fixed g-100g soil		pH		N.fixed g-100g soil		pH				
	N.fixed at 16 m.e. of Ca-salts per 100g (X × 10 ²)	Increased than value in control lbs./acres (X × 10 ²)	Initial	Final	N.fixed at 16 m.e. of Ca-salts per 100g (X × 10 ²)	Increased than value in control lbs./acres (X × 10 ²)	Initial	Final	N.fixed at 16 m.e. of Ca-salts per 100g (X × 10 ²)	Increased than value in control lbs./acres (X × 10 ²)	Initial	Final			
CaCO ₃	10.56	1.54	231.00	8.65	9.30	9.92	0.92	133.00	8.75	8.90	10.64	1.84	276.00	8.50	9.35
CaHPO ₄	9.84	0.82	123.00	8.50	8.35	8.61	0.61	90.50	8.45	8.30	9.60	0.80	120.00	8.35	8.35
CaO	10.08	1.01	159.00	8.85	9.00	9.60	0.60	90.00	8.90	9.15	9.36	0.56	54.00	8.85	9.10
CaSO ₄	10.40	1.38	205.00	8.30	7.20	10.24	1.24	86.00	8.15	8.00	10.80	2.00	300.00	8.00	7.90
CaSO ₃	9.84	0.78	117.00	8.80	8.35	9.60	0.60	90.00	8.60	8.35	10.80	0.80	120.00	8.65	8.25
CaS	10.88	1.86	279.00	7.95	7.75	10.40	1.40	210.00	9.00	7.75	10.78	1.98	283.00	7.95	7.50
Ca(CH ₃ COO) ₂	10.80	1.78	267.00	8.15	8.20	9.80	0.80	120.00	9.65	8.50	10.82	2.02	300.30	8.15	8.00
Ca-citrate	11.10	2.08	301.20	8.40	8.00	10.32	1.32	198.00	8.60	8.55	10.64	1.84	276.00	8.50	8.15
Control	9.02	—	—	8.60	8.50	9.00	—	—	8.50	8.50	8.30	—	—	8.60	8.50

may be applied here. According to them as the bacterial respiration proceeds a special enzyme 'A' gets hydrogenated to AH_2 , which is then changed by oxidation (by H_2O_2 formed in respiration) to a free radical AH . This radical then binds atmospheric nitrogen forming N_2H_2 . The reaction may be shown in the following equational forms :

This hydrogenation obviously will be more effective with the reduction in soil pH as observed in our soils treated with different calcium salts. Reaction (3), shows that the special respiratory enzyme, 'A', is free again for further hydrogenation and nitrogen

fixation. It may be pointed in the end that calcium being an essential element, its presence will help in carrying out normally the activities of the nitrogen fixing aztobacters.

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